

Subject: Expression of Interest and Support for the Horizon Europe Project iRELIANCE

Zaragoza, January 26, 2026

To whom it may concern,

Ebro Hydrographic Confederation (Confederación Hidrográfica del Ebro, CHE), based in Spain, has been informed by Eurecat about the Horizon Europe project **iRELIANCE**. CHE is the Ebro River Basin Authority under the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge of the Spanish Government.

The iRELIANCE project aims to develop knowledge, methodologies, and decision-support tools to enable effective **cross-sectoral decision-making** for **water–energy–food–ecosystem (WEFE) resource management** at river basin scale, under conditions of **deep climate, socio-economic, and geopolitical uncertainty**, with the ultimate objective of strengthening **water systems resilience**.

The objectives of iRELIANCE, as well as the knowledge and tools it seeks to generate, are of **strategic relevance** to CHE, particularly in light of the new **European Water Resilience Strategy** and the increasing challenges posed by climate change, extreme events, competing water uses and, in recent times, geopolitical instability. These developments require new approaches to long-term strategic planning and operational decision-making that explicitly address uncertainty and cross-sectoral interdependencies.

In this context, the iRELIANCE project is both **timely and critically important**. The project's focus on integrated, participatory, and scenario-based approaches for decision-making under deep uncertainty can provide valuable support to long-term strategic planning for water systems; operational decision-making under uncertainty; cross-sectoral dialogue among water, energy, agriculture, and ecosystem actors; informed discussions with governmental bodies and relevant agencies on policy development; transparent and equitable discussions with water users on water allocation, use, and availability.

Accordingly, CHE hereby expresses its **interest and willingness to contribute** to the iRELIANCE project through the following activities, as relevant to the Lower Ebro:

- engaging in content-related discussions and workshops for the **co-creation of knowledge, methodologies, and decision-support tools**;
- contributing expertise, insights, and feedback from practice to ensure the **relevance and applicability** of project outputs;
- sharing our network to support **stakeholder engagement**, data collection, sharing of lessons learned, and uptake of project results;
- participating in the **validation and testing** of iRELIANCE knowledge, tools, and approaches;
- supporting the **dissemination and exploitation** of project results for policy, planning, and practice.

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El Jefe de la Oficina de Planificación Hidrológica - Miguel Angel Garcia Vera. Sello de tiempo: 26/01/2026 19:11:42

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We believe that collaboration within the iRELIANCE project can create significant added value, both for the project and for our organisation, by strengthening evidence-based and inclusive approaches to resilient water and related resource management.

We look forward to future collaboration with the iRELIANCE consortium and remain available for any further information or clarification.

Kind regards,

Miguel Ángel García Vera
Jefe de la Oficina de Planificación Hidrológica
Confederación Hidrográfica del Ebro